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Radiodermatitis and Radionecrosis During and After Radiation Therapy for Vulvar Cancer: A Case Report

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Introduction: Squamous cell vulvar carcinoma is a tumor with limited radiosensitivity, requiring high doses of radiation therapy (RT) for favourable therapeutic response. The irradiated volume must include not only the tumor and regional lymphatics, but also surrounding skin (groin, pubis, vulva, perineum and sometimes the skin of the gluteal region), which increases the likelihood of radiodermatitis that is an expected complication, whether early or late. Timely and appropriate local care can help delay grade I-II skin reactions and prevent severe reactions (grade III-IV radioepithelitis) and minimize interruptions of RT treatment, which can negatively affect therapeutic outcomes. Treatment of radionecrosis (grade IV) is complex and often requires hospitalization.

Case Report: A 74-year-old woman with FIGO stage IIIb squamous cell vulvar carcinoma underwent radical RT. She received a total dose (TD) of 60Gy to the vulva and 54Gy to the regional lymphatics, with an additional brachytherapy boost to the residual tumor (2x7Gy). After 22 radiation fractions, the patient developed grade II/III radiodermatitis despite intensive local care. The condition required three short treatment pauses, during which topical corticosteroids were applied. Once the skin recovered, RT was completed. However, three months post-treatment, radionecrosis of the vaginal introitus and vulva was observed due to inadequate post-radiation care, despite complete tumor regression. This complication required hospitalization and complex local and systemic therapy (antibiotics, infusions).

Conclusion: Early detection and complex care for radiodermatitis (e.g., Gentian violet 1% solution, charcoal and silver-based dressings, hyaluronic acid vaginalette) can reduce treatment pauses and improve outcomes.

Keywords: vulvar carcinoma, radiodermatitis, local care

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